

THE SIGNIFICANCE AND DILEMMAS OF TEACHING PHRASEOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7110393>

Abstract. *This article illustrates teaching phraseology which is the side of significance and dilemmas of teaching in English and Uzbek languages. Particularly, it presents the scholars opinions and their researches and it is given general conclusions.*

Keywords: *phraseology, phraseme, linguistic competence, communicative competence, pedagogical description.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ И ДИЛЕММЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИИ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *Данная статья иллюстрирует преподавание фразеологии, которая является стороной значения и дилеммы преподавания на английском и узбекском языках. В частности, представлены мнения ученых и их исследования, даны общие выводы.*

Ключевые слова: *фразеология, фразема, языковая компетенция, коммуникативная компетенция, педагогическая характеристика.*

INTRODUCTION

Each country reflects a few kind of conventions through appearing their moves, outlining their exercises or utilizing assortment of dialects. It is known that individual has a place to this national culture, dialect, history, writing. Language isn't as it were the social association in the midst of the individuals, but moreover it is affixed with the culture. Subsequently, when we learn a language we moreover pay consideration the culture of this nation. In expansion to this, manner which is the department of the language appears the culture and conventions of that nation by utilizing phraseological units in communicative competence. Today, it is causing to appear linguo- culturology the economic-political, cultural and scientific relations between people, nations, countries as well as international cultural communicative processes, the interaction of languages in the field of linguistics. As a result, this brings a bunch of dilemmas and challenging of teaching phraseology in different languages. It is forever conversed the significance as well as difficulties of teaching phraseological studies as it illustrates the correlation between the language and the society. The issues of teaching word-components in a phraseological unit is occupied the center of phraseology in this article.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There's a huge sum of philosophical analysis on the issue of this concept. One of the most reasons for educating expressiveness is that "phraseological competence", knowing a suitable number of phraseological things and knowing how to utilize these things effectively in setting, is basic for learners. Phraseological competence is a crucial part of linguistic competence or communicative competence, [1: p 48] and more importantly the skill of using phraseological items properly in context is indispensable to achieving native-like competence [2: p 242]. Similarly, as argued by Meunier and Granger [3: p 119-139], "phraseology should occupy a central and uncontroversial position in instructed second language acquisition". The

primary works on Uzbek manner showed up within the early 50s of the final century. Among them are the papers of Sh.Rahmatullaev, Ya.D.Pinkhasov, A.Shomaksudov, M.Khusanov [4: p 24]. In these works, expressions within the Uzbek dialect are analyzed on the premise of the structural-semantic classification of academician V.V.Vinogradov, expressions are separated into phraseological units, phraseological disarrays and phraseological compounds. However, we have not yet encountered the problem and significance of teaching phraseological units in Uzbek language. This field is also vital in our classroom. Due to the fact students should understand and are aware of phraseological combinations and units in their future.

RESULTS

Scholars endeavor to find absolutely vital sides of teaching phraseology in English and Uzbek languages. The reason for that teaching phraseology brings a few misunderstandings for learners, especially in translation. However, translating free word combination is not causing too much challenges. At usual, free combinations are not challenging for translation, nonetheless, if there is figurative meaning in one word there will be troublesome to overset that word from one language to another. It can be seen several types of phraseological units in English language and it demands variety as well as separate approaches to translate them into Uzbek language. Let's see some good examples concerning this one.

Adjective + noun. Both of them are different parts of speech and their features are assorted too.

Busy body- hammaning ishiga burun suqadigan odam.

There able to see the pragmatic meaning since the interpretation of one by one isn't break even with as their semantic meaning. "busy" it implies "band", "body" – "tana" in Uzbek dialect. In any case, it gives completely another meaning within the phraseological unit. In case we decipher it one at a time it gives semantic meaning that "band tana", on the flip side of the coin, there's down to business meaning in this word that being said "a individual who sticks his nose in everyone's work". This phraseme cannot be utilized deciphered the strategy of word by word. Metaphorical meaning is the most part in this phraseme. There for everybody to see, such kind of issues are experienced in Uzbek language. In English, in most cases, it is difficult to distinguish which words characterize things (they can be both things and descriptive words). For case, it could appear problem to get a handle on a concept completely and altogether at a look what the express "retail magnanimity business" implies, since it can be mindful of the meaning in two ways. Within Uzbek language, such cases barely take put. Another include of English expressions is that the descriptive word characterizing the thing is overlooked. For illustration, let's take the state as an illustration "dry pruning". The exacting interpretation of this state is "dry bush". The meaning of the word combination speaks to the bushing done when the branches of the tree are dry. Within the handle of interpretation, it is fundamental to require into thought into the semantic and basic highlights of word combinations. To begin with of all, it is prescribed to interpret the thing, since no matter what definition is utilized, everything determines the thing and the thing communicates the foremost crucial indication within the sentence.

The next task of the duration of translating is to apart from the referent groups in the sentence. After dividing the existence group of the sentence, the type of grammatical relations between the noun and the adjective is determined. The words that come before the noun determine it, if the sentence is translated from English to Uzbek, it is based on the rules of Uzbek grammar, and vice versa, if the sentence is translated from Uzbek to English, then English is translated based on the norms of language grammar. In most cases, the content of English and

Uzbek free combinations can match in both languages: Fergana State University – Farg’ona Davlat Universiteti.

DISCUSSION

The significance of teaching phraseology belongs to consciousness is the one of the difficulties of English and Uzbek language. For example, Biber [5: p 371-405] has examined the representation of phraseology in university classroom teaching and course-books by comparing the frequency of the use of lexical bundles, and the results indicate surprisingly that course-book authors do not incorporate more lexical bundles in the course-books despite a heavy reliance on bundles in classroom teaching. Indeed, he defined the main weak point of phraseological units in teaching as well as the pivotal side of teaching in phraseme. Similarly, Meunier and Gouverneur (2007) have investigated the treatment of phraseology in five general advanced EFL course-books and suggested that a number of aspects related to phraseology could still be improved in these course-books, e.g. the metalanguage used to refer to phraseology and the way phraseological exercises are integrated in the course-books. Nowadays these books are used for resolving issues which encounter in teaching phraseologies at classroom. In Römer’s (2006) survey on pedagogic materials, she also concludes that with regard to the phraseological nature of language, there are “considerable mismatches between naturally occurring English and the English that is put forward as a model in pedagogical descriptions” [6: p 126]. Therefore, it is important that both teachers and course-book writers raise their awareness of the significance of phraseology in language teaching. In my opinion, detached phraseological lessons should be taught at school. In addition to this that, the students of faraway places will have opportunity to determine and learn the phraseological units. Owing to the fact this combination is crucial to learn and to do scientific researches when they study at school.

Another reason that manner should be instructed in academic materials or classrooms is that learners regularly have issues in utilizing phraseological units viably. The way manner is utilized by learners in Uzbekistan in their essays is not totally palatable, particularly compared to the way it is utilized by ‘native’ speakers of English. For occasion, the comes about from the current consider recommend that the learners tend to utilize a limited assortment of phraseological combination and units over and over in their papers whereas showing up to utilize once in a while many other phraseological items which happen as often as possible within the English language. When I am checking my students’ essays and compositions I always face these issues on my students’ masterpieces. A good example for this that:

“I have a big family” it is true but not phraseological combination.

Instead of this, students should use “I have extended family”.

The next dilemma is brought into a relation to the methodology of teaching phraseology. As stated by Kennedy [7: p 38], “here is no tried and true ‘method’ for teaching phraseology”. Meunier and Gouverneur have also indicated that “information on the selection of learning and teaching-prone formulaic sequences is nowhere to be found, and precise guidelines on how to teach formulaic sequences [are] just as scarce”. In other words, not only is there no fixed and ‘solid’ methodology for teaching phraseology, but few useful methods have been suggested as to how it should be taught [8: p 89]. As the scholars mentioned there are not any methods for teaching and explaining the phraseological units not only at schools but also at universities in Uzbekistan. I believe that if there is any methodology in teaching combinations, most challenges will be settled by favorable sides

CONCLUSIONS

This article has given the hypothetical premise for the current consider on the asking of phraseological units. I have talked about the importance and issues of expressiveness in educating as well as examining, proposed the criteria for distinguishing and depicting phraseological combinations and presents the noteworthiness and challenging side of the scope of expressiveness in instructing and learning. I have at that pointed looked into past ponders on expressiveness which uncovers that a huge number of early considers on expressivity have concentrated on the frame of the dialect instead of the development of meaning. The crevice shows that it is advocated for the current think about to center on the connection between manner and the development of the meaning in talk. Also, it is proposed that a corpus based strategy can especially advantage the current examination of manner. I have outlined the pivotal of phraseological units in dialect learning, instructing and appeared the dilemmas of teaching phraseology.

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